

ANALYSIS OF THE DEMOGRAPHIC SITUATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKISTAN

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Annotation: In these three articles, the growth of the population of the districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is shown by the population, gender composition, by districts and by separate statistical groups.

Keywords: population, demography, growth dynamics, migration balance, birth rate, death rate, natural growth, national structure.

Today, the formation of a new socio-economic environment in the world requires conducting in-depth theoretical and practical research related to economic-demographic development. Economic-demographic problems in developed countries are primarily related to the high number and share of older people in the age structure of the population, while in most developing countries this problem is related to the increase in the number and weight of children and adolescents. This situation creates additional problems for both society and the economy. The fact that the birth rate has a large change within the countries and regions of the world, the death rate is still high compared to the large countries of India, China, and Russia, and the high percentage of deaths of children and infants indicates that the demographic crisis has entered these and other countries. A very deep demographic crisis in Russia does not allow to ensure even a normal population renewal (the natural population growth rate is negative 1.1 per thousand).

The Republic of Karakalpakstan is also characterized by the complexity of some economic and demographic problems. In particular, infant, child and maternal mortality rates are still relatively high, the average life expectancy of the population is short, and the unemployment rate is high, etc. Therefore, studying the economic and demographic development and problems of the region and developing

appropriate scientific and practical proposals for solving them on a scientific basis is of urgent importance. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev stated that the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the economy and people's lives, which has been occurring in the world in recent years, and its elimination in the conditions of Uzbekistan, are the most important tasks that must be carried out "to implement the tasks defined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan". From this point of view, special attention is paid to "development of human capital, employment of the population, and further strengthening of social support of the population living in the Aral Bay region" [1].

The last two decades of the 21st century were a turning point for many countries of the world, including the Republic of Karakalpakstan (QR), which went through market reforms. Economic reform is carried out under certain conditions, which affects all areas of life, including the demographic situation, because the population is a factor that accelerates or slows down social development.

The number and composition of the population to a certain extent affects the economic situation of the country. Consider the demographic situation in the QR 2003-2024 and determine the main trend of the QR population development.

Table 1

The dynamics of the average annual population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the absolute and indicators relative development rate in 2003-2024.

Years	Average annual population, thousand people	The absolute increase in the average annual population, thousand people		Absolute deceleration (absolute acceleration) thousand people.	Growth rate Average annual population, %	
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2003	1559,7					
2004	1567,6	7,9	7,9		100,5	100,5
2005	1571,8	4,2	12,1	-3,7	100,3	100,8

2006	1582,4	10,6	22,7	6,4	100,7	101,5
2007	1604,8	22,4	45,1	11,8	101,4	102,9
2008	1629,3	24,5	69,6	2,1	101,5	104,5
2009	1639	9,7	79,3	-14,8	100,6	105,1
2010	1680,2	41,2	120,5	31,5	102,5	107,7
2011	1693,6	13,4	133,9	-27,8	100,8	108,6
2012	1711,7	18,1	152	4,7	101,1	109,7
2013	1736,2	24,5	176,5	6,4	101,4	111,1
2014	1763,1	26,9	203,4	2,4	101,5	112,6
2015	1791,1	28	231,4	1,1	101,6	114,2
2016	1817,5	26,4	257,8	-1,6	101,5	115,7
2017	1842,3	24,8	282,6	-1,6	101,4	117,1
2018	1869,8	27,5	310,1	2,7	101,5	118,6
2019	1898,3	28,5	338,6	1	101,5	121,1
2020	1923,7	25,4	364	-3,1	101,3	122,4
2021	1948,5	24,8	388,8	-0,6	101,3	123,7
2022	1976,3	27,8	416,6	3	101,4	125,1
2023	2002,7	26,4	443	-1,4	101,3	126,4

• Source: developed by the author on the basis of statistical data of QR Statistical Committees for a short period until 2024.

To do this, we use forecasting methods based on the average growth rate by adjusting analytical trends, and the data in Table 2 show that the population of the QR will continue to grow at the beginning of the 21st century. The accuracy of the forecast was evaluated using the estimated error and the coefficient of discrepancy.

Table 2

The average annual forecast of the population of the QR until 2028 is a thousand people

years	2024	2025	2026	2027
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On the basis of stealth all sur'ati	1923,7	1948,5	1976,3	2002,7
Analytical method alignment	3820,8	3844,1	3867,4	3890,7

So it was revealed. Prediction obtained by analytical leveling method gives more accurate values. Both methods of extrapolation of trends are used, the prediction is the simplest and therefore the most approximate.

Describing the current trends in the change of the birth rate, it should be said that the processes of depopulation most strongly cover the indigenous population of the republic; population forecast that methods give approximately the same trend of absolute population growth. Thus, it can be said that in 2024 the population of the QR will be 2002.7 thousand people. The growth rate of the republic's population will be lower than that of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The work carried out allows us to conclude that the number of QR will increase in the near future, and therefore all the trends listed above will continue and worsen.

A relatively high birth rate and a low, stable overall death rate in the Republic of Karakalpakstan ensures a relatively high natural population increase. However, the demographic potential of the region is declining. The economic factor affects this. In particular, due to the conditions of the market economy, as a result of the introduction of free prices for daily consumer goods, the devaluation of money, and the constant increase in transport service and utility service fees, families are experiencing great economic and social stress.

Used literature:

- [1] Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. 28.01.2022.
- [2] Basic indicators of socio-economic development of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. - Nukus, 1991-2021.
- [3] Embergenov N.J., Khodjaeva G.A., Allanazarov K. Prirost naseleniya Republic of Karakalpakstan. Science and education in Karakalpakstan. No. 2, 2017. 37 p.